

DiSSCo Transition Project

Pilot integration of Machine Learning-assisted services for data enrichment (such as SDR) with DSarch to create a coherent framework enabling seamless integration of machine-annotated data with the Digital Specimens

Work Package 3 - Milestone 16

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Executive Summary

DiSSCo envisioned a “machine learning as a service” (MLaaS) framework in the course of its development phase DiSSCo Prepare. As the implementation and elaboration of the core technical components evolve, the need for guidance and recipes detailing the connection of additional services, including services for machine annotation, to the core Digital Specimen architecture (DS arch) emerges.

The aim of the report presented here is to extend DiSSCo’s service portfolio with new features, specifically the quantitative morphological analysis of leaflets on herbarium specimen, and to employ this use case to provide a blueprint for the integration of ML-based services into DS arch.

Keywords

DiSSCo RI, Digital Specimen Architecture, machine learning, data annotation, FAIR Digital Object, image processing, Mask R-CNN, Machine Annotation Services

List of abbreviations

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DS arch - Digital Specimen architecture

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

ML - Machine Learning

MLaaS - Machine Learning as a Service

MS - Milestone

RFC - Request For Comments

RI - Research Infrastructure

ROI - Region of Interest

WP - Work Package

GBIF - Global Biodiversity Information Facility

SAM - Segment Anything Model

IoU - Intersection over Union

MAS - Machine Annotation Service

1. Introduction

The loss of biodiversity in the Anthropocene, intensified by climate change, has a significant impact on human societies by reducing the benefits—designated as Ecosystem Services—that humans derive from ecosystems and the environment (Pfortner et al. 2021). Natural Science Collections, including in particular their enriched and annotated digital representations, have a pivotal role in the assessment and analysis of the current and future biodiversity loss by providing the fundamental baseline data collection reflecting the actual and past dynamics of marine, freshwater and terrestrial biodiversity. A major aim of the DiSSCo's infrastructure ecosystem is thus to open up specimen data and make it widely reusable in compliance with the FAIR Principles (Koureas et al. 2023), implying that data is made ready for both discovery by humans and as well for (semi-) autonomous processing by machines (i.e. machine-actionability, Jacobsen et al. 2020).

DiSSCo developed its core data model based on the broader approach of FAIR Digital Objects to represent the physical specimen digital domain (Islam et al. 2020, Wittenburg et al 2023): A Digital Specimen in the scope of DiSSCo encompasses and persistently links to all information artefacts, which are about this physical specimen including (according to the respective specimen type) sequence data, images, chemical measurements or taxonomic determinations. In this way, an object-centred and machine-interpretable representation of a specimen and its connections is realised, which makes self-contained operations on this digital object by machines possible, e.g. machine learning-based annotation of scanned images and extraction of associated data such as labels (Hardisty 2022).

Building on a pilot study to detect and classify regions of interest (ROI) on herbarium scans (Younis et al. 2020), an extended approach, enabling quantitative determinations of morphological parameters based on object instance segmentation (He et al. 2017), was developed and integrated into the functioning DiSSCo service infrastructure (Leeflang et al. 2022).

The wider objective of establishing a “machine learning as a service” (MLaaS, Grieb 2021) framework for DiSSCo is to mobilise traceable geo- and biodiversity data at scale and across domain boundaries for the large analysis and prognosis infrastructures set up currently in the context of the so-called Common European Data Spaces (Scerri et al. 2022), which could significantly increase visibility and subsequent use of collection data.

This report is organised as follows: In the next section, we outline the components developed for the Machine Annotation Service. Afterwards, we present the first results achieved using the framework with Senckenberg's herbarium collection. The final section concludes the paper detailing directions for further developments.

2. Methods

2.1. Model Selection

The transition from object detection to instance segmentation addresses the more precise delineation of specimen features allowing for detailed morphological analysis essential for biodiversity studies. Instance segmentation enables the model to identify individual object boundaries and an instance-level segmentation mask to each object. This is particularly beneficial for distinguishing closely positioned or overlapping specimen parts such as individual leaves, stems and flowers. For this project, Mask R-CNN was chosen as the instance segmentation model due to its compatibility with existing object detection methodologies and its ability to easily adapt from Faster R-CNN (Shaoqing Ren et al. 2016), the model previously used in the pilot study.

2.2. Dataset Preparation

The dataset used in organ segmentation consists of 652 images of herbarium scans sourced from the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN) vascular plant collection in Paris (Le Bras et al. 2017). These images are openly accessible through the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) portal (MNHN and Chagnoux 2020) and were originally annotated for object detection of plant organs in a previous study (Younis 2020).

For this instance segmentation project, the original annotations were further refined by generating detailed pixel-level masks for each plant organ using the Segment Anything Model (SAM) (Kirillov et al., 2023). This approach enhances the dataset, allowing for precise segmentation of individual features in each herbarium scan, supporting more detailed morphological analysis.

In addition to instance segmentation, the model was further trained to detect the scale and calculate the surface area of plant organs. The training dataset consists of 167 annotated images sourced from the Senckenberg herbarium and open-access images from the GBIF portal (Senckenberg 2020) where the scales in the images are annotated and masks are created.

2.3. Model Training and Testing

The Mask R-CNN model (He et al., 2018) is trained using PyTorch to achieve instance segmentation on digitised herbarium scans (Paske 2019). Out of 652 images, 497 annotated images were used for training, and 155 images were used for testing. Data transformations such as random horizontal and vertical flips, colour jitter, scaling, and rotation were applied during training to introduce variability and to enhance the model's generalizability.

The Mask R-CNN model used a ResNet-50 backbone to balance feature extraction quality and computational efficiency for segmenting high-resolution herbarium

images. Training strategies, such as early stopping with a patience threshold, were employed to avoid overfitting. Additionally, the model was customised with a modified RPN anchor generator and adjusted ROI heads to improve performance on the dataset.

Model performance was evaluated through metrics such as Intersection over Union (IoU) for segmentation accuracy and precision and recall for object detection reliability across the plant organs. To test model generalisation, inference was conducted on an additional specimen from the Frankfurt Senckenberg herbarium, outside of the original dataset. The model's segmentation of this external specimen validated its adaptability and potential for broader application across biodiversity datasets.

2.4. Detection of scale and organ surface area calculation

The Mask R-CNN model was trained to detect the scale within the herbarium images which is then used for calculating the surface area of plant organs. Out of 167 images, 124 images were used for training and 43 were used for testing.

Once the scale is detected by the model, Tesseract OCR is employed to extract the numerical values from the scale present in the images (Smith 2007). The distance between the numbers on the scale is then calculated and the number of pixels corresponding to 1 cm is determined. This information is used to establish a conversion factor between pixels and real-world measurements. Finally, the model uses this scale to compute the surface area of the detected plant organs converting pixel measurements into square centimetres (cm²) for accurate area calculation. This additional functionality supports detailed morphometric analysis of herbarium specimens.

2.5. Machine Learning as a Service

The DiSSCo architecture and the plant organ segmentation annotation service communicate to process annotation requests submitted in the DiSSCo environment. Figure 1 further illustrates the process flow between DiSSCo and the Plant Organ Segmentation Machine Annotation Service.

Figure 1: Schematic Overview of the Information Flow Between DiSSCo and MAS Workflow

In the DiSSCo Core architecture, a request for a Machine Annotation Service, such as the Plant Organ Segmentation can be requested through the API or user frontend (DiSSCover). This request will place a message in a Kafka queue which will trigger the scale-up of a small Machine Annotation Service (MAS) which wraps around the Plant Organ Segmentation. The Machine Learning as a Service API is hosted via Uvicorn on a virtual machine (VM). The API receives the image URLs as input from DiSSCo's Kafka producer through HTTP POST requests. Upon receiving an image URL, the API adds the message to a processing queue which forwards the message to a WebSocket service hosted on a server for plant organ segmentation.

The model then performs plant organ segmentation and scale detection on the image and sends the output information from the herbarium sheet, including the additional metadata information for the segmented organs such as bounding box coordinates, class labels, confidence scores, and area in pixels. If the scale detection is successful, then both a pixel-to-centimetre conversion ratio and an area calculation in cm² are also sent. Once processed, this information is sent back to the Uvicorn API which relays the results to the DiSSCo wrapper. This processed data is then structured into an annotation event in accordance with the OpenDS specification and published back to DiSSCo's Core architecture by placing it on another Kafka topic, making it available for downstream applications. This workflow automates the extraction of enriched metadata-rich annotations from biodiversity specimens supporting scalable and compliant data processing within DiSSCo's FAIR-aligned ecosystem.

3. Results

The Mask R-CNN model was applied to herbarium images from the Senckenberg collection, where it first identified distinct plant organs such as leaves, stems, flowers, roots, and seeds. Figure 2 below shows an example of object detection inference performed by Mask R-CNN model on a herbarium sheet.

Figure 3: Plant organ segmentation

There are overlapping organs, especially in areas with multiple leaves or flowers in close proximity which remains a challenge. This overlap reduces boundary clarity and highlights an area where further model refinement could improve performance.

In addition to organ detection, the model features a scale detection component that successfully identifies scales in all Senckenberg images used for inference. Figure 4 provides an example where the model detected the scale on a herbarium sheet.

Figure 4: Scale detection

Once the scale is detected, the model could further detect the pixel-to-centimetre ratio enabling surface area calculations for each organ in real-world units (cm²). However, variations in scale standards across images necessitate further training to improve scale detection.

Using Tesseract OCR on the detected scales, the pipeline successfully identified consecutive numeric digits in around 75% of the images, allowing for surface area calculations in most cases. When OCR was successful, the output provided an area in cm² for each segmented organ, enhancing the potential for morphometric analysis and biodiversity studies. Figure 5 shows the detected plant organs and scale with bounding boxes, class labels and confidence scores. Additionally, Figure 5 illustrates the segmentation mask alongside the organ surface area calculations.

The Kafka-based pipeline integrated with Uvicorn API and WebSocket services provides a scalable, asynchronous framework for managing high-throughput data streams in line with DiSSCo's FAIR principles for accessible and reusable data. The pipeline's flexibility allows it to be extended for other datasets and segmentation tasks which promises broader applications in biodiversity informatics. Some challenges emerged during implementation, particularly on scale detection, due to varying types of scales present in different herbarium sheets. The scale markings are often very small, which causes difficulties for OCR systems to interpret the values. The fine gradations on scales often lead to errors in recognition as OCR struggles to identify such small numbers. Additionally, the presence of various scale types further complicates the process as the OCR system is not optimised for all formats. To address these issues, further improvement of OCR's ability to detect fine markings will enhance its adaptability to various scale types. The pipeline establishes a strong foundation for biodiversity data processing to extract additional information on herbarium sheets, with future directions to further enhance the scale detection and batch processing of herbarium sheets for faster real-time performance.

5. References

- Grieb J, Weiland C, Hardisty A, Addink W, Islam S, Younis S, Schmidt M (2021) Machine Learning as a Service for DiSSCo's Digital Specimen Architecture. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 5: e75634. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.5.75634>
- Hardisty A, Brack P, Goble C, Livermore L, Scott B, Groom Q, Owen S, Soiland-Reyes S; The Specimen Data Refinery: A Canonical Workflow Framework and FAIR Digital Object Approach to Speeding up Digital Mobilisation of Natural History Collections. *Data Intelligence* 2022; 4 (2): 320–341. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00134
- He K, Gkioxari G, Dollár P, Girshick R. Mask R-CNN. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision, Venice-Italy, 2017*; pp.2961–2969. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2018.2844175>.
- Islam, S., Hardisty, A., Addink, W., Weiland, C. and Glöckler, F. (2020) 'Incorporating RDA Outputs in the Design of a European Research Infrastructure for Natural Science Collections', *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), p. 50. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-050>.
- Jacobsen, A., de Miranda Azevedo, R., Juty, N., Batista, D., Coles, S., Cornet, R., Courtot, M., Crosas, M., Dumontier, M., Evelo, C., Goble, C., Guizzardi, G., Kryger Hansen, K., Hasnain, A., Hettne, K., Heringa, J., Hooft, R., Imming, M., Jeffery, K., Kaliyaperumal, R., Kersloot, M., Kirkpatrick, C., Kuhn, T., Labastida, I., Magagna, B., McQuilton, P., Meyers, N., Montesanti, A., van Reisen, M., Rocca-Serra, P., Pergl, R., Sansone, S., Bonino da Silva Santos, L., Schneider, J., Strawn, G., Thompson, M., Waagmeester, A., Weigel, T., Wilkinson, M., Willighagen, E., Wittenburg, P., Roos, M., Mons, M., Schultes, E.; FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations. *Data Intelligence* 2020; 2 (1-2): 10–29. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_r_00024
- Koureas D, Livermore L, Alonso E, Addink W, Alves MJ, Casino A, Cural L, Enghoff H, Guiraud M, Hardy H, Hoffmann J, Landel S, Paleco C, Petersen M, Scory S, Smith VS, Weiland C, Wesche K, Woodburn M (2023) DiSSCo Prepare Project: Increasing the Implementation Readiness Levels of the European Research Infrastructure. *Research Ideas and Outcomes* 9: e113906. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.9.e113906>
- Shaoqing Ren, Kaiming He, Ross Girshick, & Jian Sun. (2016). Faster R-CNN: Towards Real-Time Object Detection with Region Proposal Networks. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1506.01497>
- Le Bras G, Pignal M, Jeanson M, Muller S, Aupic C, Carré B, Flament G, Gaudeul M, Gonçalves C, Invernón V, Jabbour F, Lerat E, Lowry P, Offroy B, Pimparé EP, Poncy O, Rouhan G, Haevermans T (2017) The French Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle vascular plant herbarium collection dataset *Scientific Data* 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.16>

MNHN, Chagnoux S (2020) The vascular plants collection (P) at the Herbarium of the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN - Paris). 69.186. GBIF. URL: <https://doi.org/10.15468/nc6rxy>

Kirillov, A., Mintun, E., Ravi, N., Mao, H., Rolland, C., Gustafson, L., Xiao, T., Whitehead, S., Berg, A., Lo, W.Y., Dollar, P., & Girshick, R. (2023). Segment Anything. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.02643>

Leeftang S, Addink W, Theocharides S (2022) Human and Machine Working Together towards High Quality Specimen Data: Annotation and Curation of the Digital Specimen. Biodiversity Information Science and Standards 6: e90987. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.6.90987>

Senckenberg (2020) Herbarium Senckenbergianum (FR). GBIF. URL: <https://doi.org/10.15468/ucmdjy>

Kaiming He, Georgia Gkioxari, Piotr Dollár, & Ross Girshick. (2018). Mask R-CNN. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1703.06870>

Paszke A, Gross S, Massa F, Lerer A, Bradbury J, Chanan G, et al. PyTorch: An Imperative Style, High-Performance Deep Learning Library. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 32 [Internet]. Curran Associates, Inc.; 2019. p. 8024–35. Available from: <http://papers.neurips.cc/paper/9015-pytorch-an-imperative-style-high-performance-deep-learning-library.pdf>

Pörtner, H.-O., Scholes, R. J., Agard, J., Archer, E., Arneth, A., Bai, X., Barnes, D., Burrows, M., Chan, L., Cheung, W. L. (William) ., Diamond, S., Donatti, C., Duarte, C., Eisenhauer, N., Foden, W., Gasalla, M. A., Handa, C., Hickler, T., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., ... Ngo, H. (2021). Scientific outcome of the IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop on biodiversity and climate change (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5101125>

Scerri, S., Tuikka, T., de Vallejo, I.L., Curry, E. (2022). Common European Data Spaces: Challenges and Opportunities. In: Curry, E., Scerri, S., Tuikka, T. (eds) Data Spaces . Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98636-0_16

Smith, R. (2007) An Overview of the Tesseract OCR Engine. 9th International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition, Brazil, 23-26 September 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDAR.2007.4376991>

Wittenburg, P., Schwardmann, U., Bianchi, C., & Weiland, C. (2023). FDOs to Enable Cross-Silo Work. Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure , 1. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.263>

Younis S, Schmidt M, Weiland C, Dressler S, Seeger B, Hickler T (2020) Detection and annotation of plant organs from digitised herbarium scans using deep learning. Biodiversity Data Journal 8: e57090. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.8.e57090>

6. Supplementary Materials

Data and materials for a trained model checkpoint as well as the necessary scripts to deploy and test the system. are available from <https://github.com/Senckenberg-DCBiodivIT/DiSSCo-MAS-Pilot>.